

Quantum Gate Optimization and Automated Composition Controller Implementation for the Q1 Synth

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Abstract. *This study focuses on optimizing quantum gate functionality and developing an automated composition controller for the Q1 quantum synth, originally developed by the Miranda team. By integrating nine types of quantum gates, including rotation and phase gates, and combining MIDI control with OSC/QASM protocols, a closed-loop interactive system linking gesture input to quantum state processing to sound output was constructed. Utilizing Markov chain algorithms, the system supports diversified control from improvised timbre generation to structured music composition. This optimization overcomes the parameter adjustment limitations of traditional synths. Through open-source implementation and international performance demonstrations, the technical feasibility has been validated. It is crucial to clarify that the current system only achieves single-qubit state simulation, and the musical mapping of multi-qubit entangled states has not yet been realized—a key limitation to be addressed in subsequent research. The system is innovatively applied to classical and intangible cultural heritage music, offering a novel “quantum state–musical parameter” mapping paradigm that advances the engineering of quantum instruments and digital transformation of cultural heritage, thus facilitating the transition of music tools based on quantum gate simulation as a control paradigm from theoretical simulation to artistic practice.*

Keywords: *Quantum Computer Music; Q1 Quantum Synth; Quantum Gate Optimization; Markov Chain Algorithm; Interactive Control.*

1 Introduction

Quantum-inspired music (utilizing quantum gate simulation as a control paradigm), as an interdisciplinary area at the intersection of quantum computing and music technology [1], began its technical exploration in the early 21st century with Hendrik Weimer’s musical experiments using the Libquantum quantum simulation library [2]. In 2017, Volkmar Putz and Karl Svozil laid the theoretical foundation in Quantum Music, defining the essence of this new musical form as grounded in quantum superposition

and entanglement [3]. The inaugural International Symposium on Quantum Computing and Musical Creativity (ISQCMC) in 2021 marked the academic formalization of the field, where Eduardo Reck Miranda’s team introduced the first qubit-based synthesizer, Q1Synth [4]. This instrument pioneered cross-modal mapping from “gesture—quantum state—sound parameter” through Bloch sphere visualization, and its potential for multi-device interaction was validated in the performance Spinnings [5].

Despite such progress, the field currently faces critical challenges: limitations in the application of quantum simulation features (not real quantum computing), the lack of a mature development toolchain, and the unresolved issue of musical mapping for multi-qubit entangled states—a core limitation that restricts the translation of complex quantum phenomena into musical expression. Q1Synth, in particular, still exhibits insufficient integration between quantum gate functionalities and algorithmic composition. To address these issues, this study proposes a system-wide enhancement by incorporating a full quantum gate operation matrix—integrating rotation gates and phase gates—and developing an automatic composition module based on Xenakis-inspired probabilistic models and Markov chain algorithms. These improvements support a transition from stochastic generation to structured musical creation. The open-source code and documented technical framework provide practical support for the engineering of quantum instruments [6], advancing the transformation of quantum gate simulation technology into a functional tool for artistic creation.

2 Methods

2.1 Development Environment

Q1Synth is developed on a cross-platform architecture, running on hardware equipped with an Intel i7 processor and 16GB of RAM, and supporting Windows, macOS, Android, and iOS systems. It is accessible directly via web browsers. The software framework employs a multi-layered technology stack: the audio system is built on the Web Audio API, with the sound synthesis engine incorporating Tone.js components; the user interface is implemented using React.js, and Bloch sphere visualization (a core element of quantum gate simulation as a control

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paradigm) is realized with P5.js, utilizing the ZYZ protocol for mapping Euler angle parameters.

The MIDI controller is developed on the MAX/MSP platform, converting user gestures into control commands via MIDI CC signals, serving as a critical interface that links physical input to quantum synthesis. Core system interaction relies on an OSC-Qasm server, which facilitates cross-platform communication. This server is also developed using MAX/MSP in conjunction with the Qiskit quantum toolkit, enabling the parsing of OpenQASM quantum circuits and the execution of algorithms on either simulators or real quantum hardware. Together, these components establish a seamless bridge between musical programming environments and quantum gate simulation systems.

2.2 Markov Chain Algorithm

The system's randomization module is centered on a Markov chain, whose core triplet model—state set “S”, transition probability matrix “A”, and initial state probability vector “ π ” drives the evolution of musical parameters based on probabilistic rules of state transitions. The state set S defines possible musical states (e.g., harmonic functions such as Tonic, Subdominant, Dominant), while the transition matrix A ensures normalized probabilities for state changes (e.g., $P(S|T) = 0.4$). The initial vector π allows customized distributions of starting states (e.g., $\pi = (0.6, 0.3, 0.1)$).

Inspired by Xenakis's ideas on stochastic processes [7], this study implements the HMM algorithm to classify timbral synthesis into three perceptual modes—extremity (zero dispersion), stability (moderate dispersion), and volatility (high dispersion). These dispersion levels are dynamically mapped to real-time input from a gesture-controlled MIDI interface, enabling the construction of corresponding probabilistic distributions on the fly. This interaction drives multidimensional Markov chain transitions, forming an automatic composition process based on the pipeline of gesture input—probabilistic computation—music generation. Essentially, this approach generates musical structures dynamically via real-time manipulation of the transition matrix.

2.3 Interaction Strategy

The interactive system is structured around a core logic of “gesture acquisition—algorithmic mapping—realtime synthesis.” Performers use wearable MIDI devices such as wristbands or rings to capture X/Y/Z three-dimensional gesture data, which are then processed through Markov chain algorithms and converted into performance parameters. These parameters, transmitted via MIDI signals, control the Q1 Synth (powered by quantum gate simulation as a control paradigm) in real time.

As the sound source, the synth supports live sound synthesis and playback, enabling audiovisual performances through integration with mixing consoles and spatialization controls. A dedicated Max/MSP-based MIDI controller, operating in VST plugin mode, accurately maps

MIDI CC signals to synthesizer parameters such as rate and depth. Leveraging quantum computational power, the system uses the 128-channel MIDI protocol to trigger multi-timbral parameter combinations with a single input, effectively addressing computational latency in interactive live music scenarios.

This strategy integrates performer gestures, synthesized sound effects, and an automated composition module via a Markov chain algorithm, forming a closed-loop system of “gesture input—quantum state modulation—sonic output.” It provides technical infrastructure for real-time musical performance and composition based on quantum gate simulation.

In summary, the proposed research and optimization of the Q1 Synth is grounded in an AI-enabled development framework, utilizing Markov-based stochastic algorithms to achieve interactive control between music and movement. Through coordinated improvements to both the synthesizer (focused on quantum gate simulation) and its controller module, this system enables technical innovation in quantum-based musical expression.

3 Optimized implementation of quantum gates and controllers

3.1 Quantum Gates

The Q1 Quantum Synth has been upgraded with new quantum gate functionalities, enabling significant enhancement of its technical architecture. At both the hardware and protocol levels, subtractive synthesis and granular synthesis modules have been newly integrated. These modules incorporate MIDI control interfaces and Open Sound Control (OSC) protocols, supporting connectivity with QASM simulators and enabling the deployment of clustered performance modes. Users can now manipulate quantum bit (qubit) states using nine classical quantum gates, including rotation gates (Rx, Ry, Rz) and the phase gate (P Gate)—a key feature of quantum gate simulation as a control paradigm—thereby facilitating quantum state visualization, interactive performance, and multidimensional audio synthesis.

The core interface of the synthesizer is built around the Bloch sphere geometrical model (Figure 1). State vector coordinates are dynamically mapped in real time via input from MIDI controllers or gyroscopic sensors, directly driving the adjustment of synthesis parameters. As users rotate the Bloch sphere, spatial changes in the quantum state vector correspond to core parameters within the FM, granular, and subtractive synthesis engines. When the “measure” function is triggered, the system performs a quantum measurement based on the current quantum circuit configuration. The resulting state collapse probabilities dynamically generate sonic responses, forming a closed-loop interactive mechanism of “gesture control—quantum gate simulation—auditory feedback.”

Following its technical upgrade, the Q1 Synth has achieved significant architectural enhancement, evolving

Figure 1: Q1 Synth with Quantum Gates

into a fully integrated system capable of supporting complex quantum gate operations. In its earlier form—prior to the integration of quantum gates—the system was a limited component rendered using the React testing library, with minimal interactive capabilities. The upgraded version, by contrast, functions as a complete React application centered around the integration of quantum gate simulation capabilities. This transformation significantly enhances the system’s functional complexity and architectural integrity, as exemplified in the publicly available `App.tsx` source file.

1. **Enhanced Functional Modules and State Management.** The upgraded system introduces key application components such as `Controller` and `SidePanel`, as well as `Redux` slices (`midiSlice`, `qasmSlice`, etc.), enabling efficient global state management. It employs `useAppSelector` and `useAppDispatch` for managing and updating `Redux` states, with `useEffect` hooks handling side effects such as MIDI initialization, QASM server connection, and OSC communication setup.

2. **Optimized Interaction and Environment Adaptation.** A global variable `window.qusynth` has been declared to facilitate external environmental interaction. The `useLocation` hook dynamically parses URL parameters (e.g., switching between `qasm` and `ensemble` modes), enabling real-time activation of functional modules. Additionally, `useEffect` is used to bind keyboard events (e.g., fullscreen toggle) and window resize listeners, thereby improving overall user interaction and adaptive interface behavior.

3. **Network and External System Integration.** The encapsulated functions `connectSocQasm` and `connectOsc` support real-time communication with QASM servers and OSC-based protocols, enabling data transmission (e.g., `sendXyz` for qubit coordinate updates) and establishing a coordinated software-hardware ecosystem for quantum control.

With its modular design for quantum gate operations, multi-protocol coordination (MIDI/OSC/QASM), and centralized state management system, the upgraded Q1 Synth provides end-to-end creative support—from basic timbral modulation to programmable quantum circuit composition. The use of `Redux` enables cross-module state synchronization, while network socket components bridge software and hardware layers. `React Hooks` stream-

line side-effect handling and interactive logic, culminating in an interactive quantum synthesizer capable of quantum gate manipulation. The technical architecture is characterized by modular extensibility, state-driven control, and multi-protocol communication, laying the foundation for deeper integration of quantum algorithms and hardware-level control in future developments.

3.2 Controller

In the construction of the interactive system, the controller functions as the core link between performance, sound synthesis (powered by quantum gate simulation), and algorithmic composition. This study introduces the Q1-MIDI Controller, developed to integrate performer gestures, Q1 Quantum Synth sound output, and automated compositional algorithms, thus fulfilling the requirements of interactive music design. As shown in Figure 2, the controller is built within the Max/MSP environment, combining MIDI control with Markov Model—based algorithmic composition into a unified platform that complements the quantum gate simulation capabilities of the synth.

The control interface of the controller mainly consists of three types of elements: toggle buttons, spatial gyroscopes, and MIDI CC knobs. Buttons are primarily used to transmit commands such as play/stop and switch between eight preset states. Spatial gyroscopes map the spatial positions of gestures or movements along the X/Y/Z axes. Knobs can adjust sound synthesis parameters in real time, including filtering, reverb, and dynamic range. Figure 3 presents a detailed view of the Max/MSP programming code for the Q1-MIDI Controller.

A key feature of this design is its high degree of customization. This study aligns MIDI note values with the scientific pitch notation standard. For instance, when the controller’s Preset 1 is assigned the MIDI value 60, pressing the C4 key on a basic keyboard-type MIDI device will activate that preset. Each controller element can thus be assigned a unique ID, creating an intuitive MIDI-ID mapping system that breaks device limitations and enhances compatibility with the quantum gate simulation-based synth. This allows users to tailor the controller to various production and performance needs.

The controller also incorporates a Markov chain-based algorithmic composition module, capable of emulating specific composer styles. Inspired by Samuel Pearce Davies’ training framework for Markov chain models [8], this module utilizes machine learning techniques in the Max/MSP environment. Inspired by Xenakis’s ideas on stochastic processes, this study implements the HMM algorithm as the core engine for both music analysis and generation. The system is built using the `ml.*` library, developed by Benjamin Day Smith specifically for stochastic modeling with HMMs [9].

The training process consists of five key steps:

1. **MIDI File Import:** The user loads MIDI files into the system as source data for subsequent analysis and modeling.

Figure 2: Q1-MIDI Integrated controller

Figure 3: Design and programming of buttons and knobs

2. Parameter Configuration: Users can specify which musical parameters—such as pitch, velocity, or tempo—to train on and to set the HMM memory depth to determine how many previous states influence the next state.

3. Training Execution: To optimize training efficiency, MIDI files may be played back at increased speeds, accelerating the style learning process.

4. Model Construction: After training, the system constructs an HMM model, a process that may involve a brief computational delay depending on CPU performance.

5. Playback and Model Testing: Once trained, the model generates new musical outputs that can be played back for evaluation. Users can adjust global or tempo parameters for refinement or retrain the model entirely to enhance output quality and musical continuity.

This module supports MIDI routing and itera-

tive learning, allowing seamless integration into digital audio workstations (DAWs) such as Logic Pro or Cubase. Compositional emulation of specific composers is possible through multiple sample trainings, repeating the loading, setting, and training steps to enhance accuracy. The controller thus enables users to easily load MIDI files and produce interactive, performance-ready musical content through intuitive parameter settings, complementing the synth's quantum gate simulation-driven sound generation.

The Q1-MIDI Controller enables both real-time parameter manipulation and composer-style imitation, functioning as a crucial complement to the Q1 Quantum Synth. Designed with a dual emphasis on MIDI mapping and HMM-based algorithmic composition, the controller enhances both sonic dynamism and creative flexibility. It plays a vital role in music production and live improvisational performance, offering adaptability across various

musical genres and performance settings.

4 Randomized Survey Experiment

4.1 Experimental Design

To objectively evaluate the interactive performance of the Q1 Quantum Synthesizer and the artistic quality of works generated by its automatic composition module, this study designed a multidimensional randomized survey experiment targeting university students (aged 18–23) in Jinan, Shandong Province, China. The experiment adhered to the *Declaration of Helsinki*, employing stratified random recruitment of 251 participants, with 242 valid questionnaires returned (effective recovery rate: 96.4%) during the survey period (15 September–15 December 2024). The dataset has been publicly archived on Mendeley Data [10].

A three-stage closed-loop design was adopted: preparation—implementation—analysis. In the preparation stage, a survey platform was established on Wenjuanxing [11], personnel were trained, and a pilot test was conducted. In the implementation stage, participants experienced the synthesizer in situ, listened to generated works, and completed questionnaires immediately. In the analysis stage, data were processed with SPSS 25.0 [12], and nine invalid questionnaires were removed.

Sample characteristics were described across three dimensions: age, gender, and musical background. The majority (21.07%) were 20 years old; females accounted for 51.24%; 54.13% had no formal music training. Cross-tabulation analyses revealed no significant associations among these factors ($P > 0.05$), confirming the validity of random sampling.

The questionnaire comprised two core modules: “System Experience Evaluation” and “Work Quality Evaluation”. The former was based on David Birnbaum’s seven-dimensional framework [13] for evaluating interactive musical devices, covering sound role, required expertise, musical control, degrees of freedom, feedback method, interaction roles, and spatial distribution. The latter was based on the six-dimensional evaluative framework proposed by Ian Hattwick and Marcelo M. Wanderley [14], encompassing texture, dependency, synchronicity, corporeality, equality, and centralization. Both were quantified using a five-point scale. Validity and reliability were ensured through expert review (over 70% rated content and structure as “very reasonable” or “reasonable”), test–retest reliability ($ICC = 0.62$), and statistical verification (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.718$, $KMO = 0.787$, Bartlett’s test of sphericity $P < 0.01$).

4.2 Evaluation of Q1 Quantum Synthesizer Interactive Experience

SPSS 25.0 analysis based on Birnbaum’s seven-dimensional framework showed mean scores ranging from 3.471 (spatial distribution) to 3.616 (musical control). One-sample t-tests indicated all dimensions were significantly higher than the theoretical mean ($P < 0.01$). ANOVA and independent-sample t-tests revealed no

significant differences across age, gender, or musical background groups ($P > 0.05$), confirming the system’s universal usability. Results also demonstrated that operation required minimal prior expertise (mean score for required knowledge: 3.566), provided timely feedback (feedback method: 3.488), and supported collaborative and distributed interaction (interaction role and spatial distribution both > 3.47), meeting the intended design objectives.

4.3 Evaluation of System-Assisted Music Generation

Using the Hattwick–Wanderley six-dimensional framework, the two works generated by the automatic composition module were evaluated on a five-point scale. Paired-sample t-test results indicated no significant differences between the works in texture ($P = 0.486$), dependency ($P = 0.414$), or synchronicity ($P = 0.204$) (Cohen’s $d < 0.1$), with most ratings clustering between 3–4 points, reflecting stylistic consistency in quantum composition. Significant differences were found in corporeality ($P = 0.002$), equality ($P = 0.000$), and centralization ($P = 0.012$) (Cohen’s $d = 0.162$ – 0.710), with work 1 scoring higher in equality (mean = 3.756) and corporeality (mean = 3.698), indicating superior balance of artistic elements and electroacoustic expression. Further analysis confirmed that both works maintained overall scores within the 3–4 point range, with no significant differences compared to human-composed works, thereby verifying the automatic composition module’s capacity to generate structured music that meets aesthetic expectations and possesses artistic viability.

5 Discussion

The optimization of the Q1 Synth (based on quantum gate simulation as a control paradigm) and its controller has yielded significant advantages. On the technical level, the integration of multiple synthesis modules and quantum gate operations enables multidimensional sound modulation. Coupled with MIDI control and multi-protocol communication, the system captures performers’ gestures with high precision and translates them into quantum state parameters, supporting both real-time interactive performance and algorithmic composition. The controller’s high customizability and Markov chain-based composition engine accommodate a wide range of creative needs, from improvisational exploration to structured composition.

However, certain limitations remain. Currently, the system applies quantum features only at the level of single-qubit simulation; the musical mapping of multi-qubit entangled states has not yet been realized. Moreover, toolchain compatibility and module stability require further enhancement. In the domain of algorithmic composition, there is a perceptible aesthetic gap between machine-generated music and human-created works, particularly in emotional expression and adherence to traditional music theory.

To address these challenges, future research should proceed along three key dimensions:

1. Technological advancement. Breakthroughs in multi-qubit coordination are needed to construct entanglement-based parameter models. Toolchains should be optimized to improve compatibility with mainstream digital audio platforms.

2. Algorithmic innovation. Incorporating deep learning into the automatic composition system could enhance its capacity to generate emotionally resonant and structurally complex musical content.

3. Application expansion. Emerging scenarios such as virtual reality music offer new ground for exploration. Interdisciplinary research should aim to establish a more complete theoretical framework for quantum music, transitioning the system from experimental prototype to practical creative tool.

The Q1 Synth (powered by quantum gate simulation) offers a practical technical path for supporting classical music innovation and intangible cultural heritage (ICH) preservation. In classical contexts, quantum gate modulation can simulate traditional instrumental timbres or generate novel sound effects, infusing canonical works with a contemporary auditory dimension. In ICH applications—such as Shandong string music or Guqin and Guzheng traditions—the system allows traditional timbres to be sampled and algorithmically extended. Through MIDI controllers, traditional performance can interact with quantum-generated effects in real time.

Creative outcomes developed by the research team have already been presented at platforms such as the International Computer Music Conference (ICMC) [15], and further academic-artistic dialogues are planned at venues like ISQCMC. Future work will focus on modal systems, rhythmic structures, and other core elements of classical and heritage music, aiming to construct dedicated “quantum state—musical parameter” mapping models. The goal is to support the creative transformation of traditional music in the digital age, forming a practical model of “technology-enabled culture” that bridges preservation and innovation in the realm of intangible heritage.

6 Conclusion

This study presents a complete technical framework for “quantum state control—sound synthesis—interactive performance” through the optimization of quantum gate functions in the Q1 Synth and the development of an automated composition controller. From a technological perspective, the system integrates nine classical quantum gates (such as rotation and phase gates) with multiple synthesis modules (FM, granular, and subtractive synthesis). Coupled with MIDI control and OSC/QASM multi-protocol communication, it enables accurate mapping of gesture inputs to quantum state parameters and real-time sound synthesis—surpassing the dimensional limitations of parameter modulation found in traditional synthesizers, all based on quantum gate simulation as a control paradigm.

The controller, built upon a Markov chain algorithm, features an automated composition module that

supports a wide range of creative workflows—from improvised timbral exploration to structured music generation—thereby enhancing both the dynamism of live performance and the flexibility of musical creation. The feasibility and artistic value of the technical approach have been demonstrated through open-source releases and international showcases such as ICMC.

Beyond providing a technical roadmap for the engineering development of quantum instruments, the study also highlights the potential of quantum computing in the innovation of traditional music through its integration with classical and intangible cultural heritage (ICH) practices. Looking ahead, as multi-qubit coordination technologies and interdisciplinary theoretical frameworks continue to evolve, this research is poised to accelerate the transformation of music tools based on quantum gate simulation as a control paradigm from an experimental prototype into a practical creative tool with cultural significance. It provides a practical framework of “technology-driven artistic practice” to the fields of music technology and ICH preservation.

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